

IMPACT BENDING BEHAVIOR OF FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE

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The behavior under the impact bending load is studied for the structural models consisting of various composites reinforced by fiber, and the experimental results are estimated by the finite element method for the objects idealized as non-homogeneous materials. As a representation of the composition, the GFRP reinforced by roving glass cloths and the GFRP reinforced by chopped strand glass mat are selected, and not only the GFRP but also the CFRP is used for considering the effects of the reinforcement. Moreover, the CFRP-GFRP-CFRP, CFRP-GFRP-Aluminum and Aluminum-GFRP-Aluminum hybrid materials are constructed to analyze the impact behavior.

From the results obtained experimentally and numerically, it is shown that the stress wave propagation mechanism is influenced by the difference of the geometrical arrangement of the reinforcement, and it gives a factor deciding the strength and the fracture mode in GFRP. In CFRP, the strength of the lateral direction to the fiber orientation becomes an important factor for the fracture. Moreover, in the hybrid composite, not only the kind of GFRP which is used for the core material but also the laminated positions of CFRP give the influence on the fracture mechanism. The analytical method adopted in this paper will be used effectively when the impact bending property of the composite having a non-homogeneous structure is estimated.

1. Introduction

In recent times, there has been significant development of various new composites and their applications. Especially the composites reinforced by fiber have been widely used in the structural elements of power craft because of their superior high specific strength as well as high modulus values. It is desirable then to analyze the behavior of composites under the impact load for the purpose of application on design of structural element. Hither, the impact characteristics have been almost estimated by the values obtained from the Charpy or Izot test. However, as the value as an impact characteristic is based on that of metals as quasi-homogeneous materials, it seems that the value dose not express the accurate characteristics of composites which have non-homogeneous arrangement of reinforcements.

In this paper, to give a guide for the effective use of the composite reinforced by fibers under the impact load and to establish the analytical method for the non-homogeneous materials, the followings are considered: First, the fracture modes under the impact load for the composites reinforced by various fibers are observed experimentally. Secondly, the flexible strain response at a few points on the specimens consisting of two layers is measured to provide a basic consideration of the stress wave propagation for the non-homogeneous materials and the results are compared with the numerical results to examine the suitability of the analytical method used in this paper. Finally, the models of composites are considered with the arrangement of the reinforcement, and the stress wave propagation in matrix-reinforcement system is measured and analyzed numerically. Then the experimental results of the non-homogeneous materials are estimated by the finite element method (FEM).

2. Fracture Modes of the Composite Materials

2.1 Test Specimens

Figure 1 shows the construction of the composite materials reinforced by various fibers. As a representation of the composition, the GFRP reinforced by roving glass cloths (R-GFRP) and the GFRP reinforced by chopped strand glass mat (M-GFRP) are selected, and not only the GFRP but also the CFRP is used for considering the effects of the reinforcement. Moreover, the GFRP-CFRP and the GFRP-Aluminum hybrid materials are constructed to analyze the impact behavior.

The resin contained within the GFRP is unsaturated polyester. And the glass fiber are given roving cloths (EWR 55) and chopped strand mat (EMG 450). Sample sheets are molded by the matched metal die after rejection of forms by a decompression-device. Aftercure is performed for 24 hours at 95°C. CFRP uses TORAY TORAYCA S-905 and allows to harden for 1 hour at 120°C. Aftercure is performed for 2 hours at 130°C. The aluminum plate used is pure aluminum (JIS 1050).

2.2 Experimental Procedure

In the present experiment, the fatigue test machine of impact bending is used. The repeated impact bending load, with the impact speed of 6.1 m/s. and the cycle of 11 c.p.m., is applied to the center of the free supported test specimen with the span of 90mm, by a falling weight of 0.3 Kg. The aspect of the growth and the propagation of the cracks caused by repeated impact bending is observed at every decremental static stiffness which is indicated by the static load P (Kg) divided the flexibility δ (mm) while increasing the number of cycles. To simplify the complex transient phenomenon the strength under

the repeated impact bending load is indicated by the value of the cycles to fracture under the constant impact energy. Moreover, the strength under the static load of the composite materials is measured previously to help the consideration of the impact bending behavior.

2.3 Experimental Results and Considerations

Table 1 shows the strength under the static load (σ_b) and the relative strength which is the ratio of the strength of each material to the strength of the R-GFRP (σ_r) or the M-GFRP (σ_m). Each GFRP has its own fracture mode. Namely the fracture of the R-GFRP is caused by the micro-buckling of the roving glass cloths in the compressive stress field. But in the M-GFRP, the fracture occurs in the tensile stress field. In the case of the hybrid materials which are reinforced by the CFRP or the aluminum plate on the GFRP lamination, the above modes occur remarkably. When the CFRP having high strength is laminated on both surfaces of the GFRP, the strength of the com-

	A	B	C	Type
1	--	CFRP	--	CF
2	--	R-GFRP	--	R
3	CFRP	R-GFRP	CFRP	CF-R-CF
4	CFRP	R-GFRP	Al	CF-R-Al
5	Al	R-GFRP	CFRP	Al-R-CF
6	Al	R-GFRP	Al	Al-R-Al
7	--	M-GFRP	--	M
8	CFRP	M-GFRP	CFRP	CF-M-CF
9	CFRP	M-GFRP	Al	CF-M-Al
10	Al	M-GFRP	CFRP	Al-M-CF
11	Al	M-GFRP	Al	Al-M-Al

thickness: CFRP 0.6mm(A,C)
 2.7mm(B)
 R-GFRP 4.3mm
 M-GFRP 4.1mm
 Al 0.5mm

Fig. 1 - Dimension and construction of the composite materials used for the static or impact bending test.

Table 1. Bending strength and the relative strength under the static load for various composites.

	σ_b (Kg/mm ²)	σ_b/σ_r		σ_b (Kg/mm ²)	σ_b/σ_m
R	35	1	M	21.8	1
CF-R-CF	55.6	1.59	CF-M-CF	53.2	2.44
CF-R-Al	46.5	1.33	CF-M-Al	27.6	1.27
Al-R-CF	41.8	1.19	Al-M-CF	44.9	2.06
Al-R-Al	36.2	1.03	Al-M-Al	22.5	1.03

Table 2. Values of cycles to fracture under the constant impact energy.

	R	86	M	77
CF-R-CF	180	CF-M-CF	150	
CF-R-Al	200	CF-M-Al	18	
Al-R-CF	225	Al-M-CF	520	
Al-R-Al	306	Al-M-Al	23	

posite materials increases remarkably, but when the aluminum plates are used as the surface materials the strength of the composite materials scarcely increases. When the CFRP and the aluminum plate are laminated on each surface of the GFRP lamination non-symmetrically, the hybrid effect shows remarkably. Namely, when the CFRP is laminated on the compressive side of the R-GFRP or on the tensile side of the M-GFRP, the strength of the composite materials becomes large as compared with the case of the contrary lamination of the surface materials. Therefore, using the most effective lamination, the effective composite materials are obtained by considering the characteristics of the reinforcements.

The above observation belongs to the static behavior of the composite materials. But it seems that the fracture mode under the impact load varies with the laminated conditions, too. A discussion of the impact bending behavior follows.

Table 2 shows the value of the cycles to fracture under constant impact energy, and Figures 2 and 3 show the decremental static stiffness under the repeated impact load for the hybrid materials belonging to the R-GFRP and to the M-GFRP, respectively. The fracture modes of the R-GFRP and the M-GFRP shown in Photo 1 are similar to the static ones. Namely, in the M-GFRP, the fracture occurs on the back surface against the loading point, but in the R-GFRP, the fracture occurs near the loading point because of a micro-buckling of the roving glass cloths. In the case of the hybrid materials reinforced by the CFRP on the impact side (CF-R-CF, CF-R-Al, CF-M-CF, CF-M-Al), the crack occurs at the impact point of the CFRP with a perpendicular direction to the fiber orientation at a few values of the cycles. And the value of the P/δ is decreased largely as shown in Figures 2 and 3. Therefore, the CFRP which is effective materials for the static load, is useless for the impact load when the CFRP is laminated on the impact surface.

Comparing all hybrid materials belonging to the R-GFRP, the CF-R-CF hybrid material has minimum value of the cycles to fracture in spite of having the maximum value of the strength under the static load. And the Al-R-Al hybrid material has maximum value of the cycles to fracture. It seems that the above happens through the increases of the value of the stress in the composite materials under constant impact energy, and the weak characteristics of the CFRP under the impact bending load. Comparing all hybrid materials belonging to the M-GFRP, the CF-M-Al and the Al-M-Al hybrid materials have a smaller value of the cycles to fracture than that for the M-GFRP with smaller thickness than that for the hybrid materials. Namely, by being hybrid lamina-

Fig. 2 - Decremental static stiffness (P/δ) under repeated impact load for the hybrid materials belonging to R-GFRP.

Fig. 3 - Decremental static stiffness (P/δ) under repeated impact load for the hybrid materials belonging to M-GFRP.

tion, the value of the cycles to fracture becomes small. The above shows the aluminum plate on the back surface has little effect as a reinforcement. But in the case of the CF-M-CF and the Al-M-CF hybrid materials, the value of the cycles to fracture becomes large because the tensile stress field of the M-GFRP is reinforced by the CFRP. Especially in the case of the Al-M-CF, the value of the cycles to fracture becomes maximum because the crack is hard to make occur at the impact point. Then under the impact load, the laminated conditions become a large factor for the fracture mode. The fracture modes of the CFRP and the hybrid composite materials are shown in Photos 2, 3 and 4 respectively.

To make some observations on the above phenomena, the impact behavior of the composite materials is analyzed experimentally and numerically from the stress wave propagation in the non-homogeneous materials by constructing the idealized non-homogeneous models. This then follows.

Photo. 1 - Fracture of R-GFRP(1) and M-GFRP(2) under repeated impact load.

Photo. 2 - Fracture of CFRP under repeated impact load.

Photo. 3 - Fracture of the hybrid composites belonging to R-GFRP under repeated impact load.
 (1) CF-R-CF, (2) CF-R-Al
 (3) Al-R-CF, (4) Al-R-Al

Photo. 4 - Fracture of the hybrid composites belonging to M-GFRP under repeated impact load.
 (1) CF-M-CF, (2) CF-M-Al
 (3) Al-M-CF, (3) Al-M-Al

3. Finite Element Analysis

Considering the non-homogeneity of the composite materials, the bending problem of the beam is analyzed as a plane strain problem by the finite element method. It is well known that using a constant strain triangular element, the bending behavior is not expressed clearly in a plane problem (1). And the estimation of the selected element for the bending problem is usually done by comparing the displacement of the cantilever with the value obtained from the beam theory. In this paper, to select an optimum element for the bending problem, a few elements are estimated by comparison with the theory of the free supported beam which agrees with the experimental method used in this paper. Figures 4 and 5 show the finite element division used for the selection of the element and Tables 3 and 4 show the calculated results obtained by using those elements. The elements with symbols A, B and C show the constant strain triangular elements and the element with a symbol D shows the rectangular element with eight nodes and the element with a symbol E shows the

Fig. 4 - Finite element models with various elements and divisions.

Fig. 5 - Various divisions used rectangular element with eight nodes.

Fig. 6 - Displacement response of various models shown in Fig. 4 under the input force shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 - Input force used for the calculation of dynamic response. (Δ shows the time incremental)

linear strain triangular element in Figure 4. When the constant strain element is used, the results express the bending behavior roughly if the element division is broken into pieces. But the calculation time and the core size in the computer are wasted in that case. On the contrary, using the high order elements shown as D, especially the element with eight nodes and E, it is easy to analyze the bending behavior even if the element division is broken into large meshes as shown in Table 4.

In the analysis of the composite materials, to consider the non-homogeneity of the materials, the aspect ratio of the length against the width sometimes increases. But in that case, the exactness of the calculated results is preserved practically by using the rectangular element. Moreover, this element is of great advantage to draw the strain or the stress distributions. Hence, the rectangular element with eight nodes is used in this paper.

Table 3. Accuracy investigation of the bending analysis for the simple supported beam with various models.

L/T	Model	F.E.M.	Beam Theory	F.E.M./Beam Theory
2	A	0.201×10^2	0.157×10^2	1.280
	B	0.158		1.006
	C	0.132		0.841
6	A	0.257×10^1	0.276×10^1	0.931
	B	0.208		0.754
	C	0.161		0.583
	D	0.281		1.018
	E	0.279		1.011
10	A	0.113	0.122	0.926
	B	0.090		0.737
	C	0.068		0.557
	D	0.123		1.008
	E	0.122		1.000
16	A	0.450	0.493	0.913
	B	0.359		0.728
	C	0.270		0.548

Table 4. Accuracy improvement with eight nodes rectangular elements.

L/T	Model	F.E.M.	Beam Theory	F.E.M./Beam Theory
10	A	0.102	0.122	0.836
	B	0.103		0.844
	C	0.120		0.984
	D	0.122		1.000
	E	0.123		1.008

The displacement in the element u, v are written as

$$u = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 x + \alpha_3 y + \alpha_4 xy + \alpha_5 x^2 + \alpha_6 y^2 + \alpha_7 x^2 y + \alpha_8 xy^2 \quad (1)$$

$$v = \alpha_9 + \alpha_{10} x + \alpha_{11} y + \alpha_{12} xy + \alpha_{13} x^2 + \alpha_{14} y^2 + \alpha_{15} x^2 y + \alpha_{16} xy^2 \quad (2)$$

and the consistent mass matrix is assembled for the dynamic response analysis.

In the dynamic response analysis, the time incremental Δt is selected by considering the value of $\sqrt{12}/\omega_{max}$ of the element. The value of ω_{max} is the maximum characteristics frequency of the element. Figure 6 shows the displacement response under the impact load shown in Figure 7 for the models shown in Figure 4. The displacement response varies with the element used under the influence of the supported points.

4. Stress Propagation in the Non-homogeneous Materials

4.1 Test Specimens

In this chapter, the idealized non-homogeneous materials with two layers are constructed as shown in Figure 8. And Table 5 shows the material constant used in the calculation.

Fig. 8 - Structural model consisting of two layers.

Fig.10 - Finite element division for structural model consisting of two layers.

Table 5. Material constants used in the calculation.

	E (Kg/mm ²)	G (Kg/mm ²)	ν	γ (g/cm ³)
Steel	21,000	8,076	0.3	7.8
Copper	11,200	4,300	0.3	8.96
Al	7,000	2,600	0.33	2.7
Glass	7,000	2,846	0.23	2.5
Acryl	370	132	0.4	1.19

Fig. 9 - Illustration of impact bending test device.

4.2 Experimental Procedure and the Finite Element Division

Figure 9 shows the illustration of the impact bending test device. The flexible strain response at a few points on the specimens is measured under the impact load by using the transient memory device, experimentally. Numerically, the model shown in Figure 10 is used for the finite element analysis. The example of the input force is the same as that in Figure 7.

4.3 Results and Considerations

Comparing the results by the finite element method (Figs. 11 and 12) to experimental results (Figs. 13 and 14) suggests that the tendency of the result is similar though the quantity shifts a little. The difference of the quantity is caused by the value of the input force and the material constants which are different, experimentally and numerically. But both results show the characteristics of the strain response cleverly. The strain response of the B point shown in Figures 11 and 12 show that the material bends conversely against the external force direction early.

Figure 15 shows the displacement response at the impact point and the opposite point of the Acryl-Steel specimens. The two cases of the lamination conditions are then calculated. The displacement at the impact point is different between the two cases nevertheless the displacement at the opposite point is completely the same. And when the impact force is loaded on the Acryl plate directly, the displacement at the impact point is larger than that of the contrary laminated case.

The material with low Young's modulus had better not be laminated at the impact surface. And the order of the lamination has much influence on the impact behavior even if each material is equal in bending stiffness EI of the composite materials.

Figure 16 shows the effect of the material constant of the layer on the back surface affecting the strain occurring in the direction of the impact force (ξy). When the material with high modulus is laminated on the back surface, the strain occurred in the layer, which is laminated at the upper side, becomes larger than that of the single material because of the reflection stress occurring on the surface between the two layers (2).

The shearing strain has a great influence upon the impact behavior of the composite materials reinforced by fibers. The value of the shearing strain is influenced by the order of lamination, excessively. By laminating Acryl plate on the upper side, the difference of the value of the shearing strain between two layers becomes large as shown in Figure 17 and the delamination is observed many times in the Acryl-Steel composite materials experimentally.

As discussed above, the effectiveness of the analytical method used in this paper is confirmed and the effect of the laminated condition is considered by using the simple models of the composite materials in this chapter. Discussion follows using idealized models about the impact behavior of CFRP, GFRP and the GFRP-CFRP hybrid materials.

Fig.11 - Strain(ϵ_x) history of steel-steel specimen in impact. (Result by FEM)

Fig.12 - Strain(ϵ_x) history of Acryl-Steel specimen in impact. (Result by FEM)

Fig.13 - Strain(ϵ_x) history of Steel-Steel specimen in impact. (Experimental result)

Fig.14 - Strain(ϵ_x) history of Acryl-Steel specimen in impact. (Experimental result)

Fig.15 - Displacement response of Acryl-Steel specimen in impact.

Fig.16 - Strain(ϵ_y) history of Acryl-Acryl, Acryl-Glass and Acryl-Steel specimens in impact.

Fig.17 - Shearing strain history of Acryl-Steel specimen in impact.

5. Dynamic Response of the GFRP, CFRP and its Hybrid Composite Materials

5.1 Calculated Models and their Material Constants

It is not possible to calculate the strict models of the composite materials because of their complex internal structures. In this chapter, CFRP is modeled considering its anisotropic characteristics and GFRP is modeled aiming the continuation or the discontinuation of the fiber. And the impact behavior of the models are considered to clear the fracture modes of the composite materials observed in chapter 2. Some of the models and their material constants used in the calculations are shown in Figure 18 and Table 6, respectively. The models excepting 1 are considered by separating the resin and the reinforcements. The elements indicated by oblique lines show the layers of reinforcements.

Table 6. Material constants used in the calculation.

	$E_x(\text{Kg/mm}^2)$	$E_y(\text{Kg/mm}^2)$	ν_x	ν_y	$G(\text{Kg/mm}^2)$	$\gamma(\sigma/\text{cm}^2)$
CFRP	13,000	1,000	0.30	0.023	700	1.55
	13,000	13,000	0.30	0.30	5,000	1.55
Resin	370	370	0.40	0.40	132	1.22
Carbon F.	23,000	1,980	0.30	0.023	4,000	1.78
Glass F.	7,000	7,000	0.23	0.23	2,846	2.50

Fig.18 - Finite element models for various composites.

Fig.19 - Deflection curves for model 1.

Fig.20 - Instantaneous distribution of the strain(ϵ_x) in the section at the center for model 1.

5.2 Anisotropic Characteristics of the Stress Wave

Almost all of the composite materials have anisotropic characteristics, and especially CFRP has a large one. The mode of the deformation under the impact load is shown in Figure 19. As compared with the materials having isotropic characteristics, the deformation area of CFRP under the impact load is narrow because of the small shearing modulus of CFRP and the deflection is large because of the small Young's modulus (E_y). Therefore, the material having anisotropic characteristics has charge of the impact load in a narrow area of the beam early.

The strain (ϵ_x) distribution in the cross section at the center for each time interval are shown in Figure 20. The stress propagation from the impact point to the back surface is late because of the small Young's modulus (E_y) of CFRP, and the influence of the impact force increases at the impact point. The above may be factors of occurrence of the cracks at the impact point of CFRP.

5.3 Non-homogeneous Characteristics of the Stress Wave

In this section, the CFRP is treated by separating the resin and the reinforcements. As shown in Figure 21, the large tensile strain occurs at the impact point early. And when the glass is considered as reinforcement substituting for the carbon fiber, the same results are obtained as shown in Figure 22. It seems that above is caused by the existence of the resin layers on the surface of the composite materials. And the phenomenon is a special feature of the composite materials with resin layers on the surfaces, though the value of the tensile strain may be varied with the change of the thickness of the resin layer. Figure 23 shows the strain distribution in the cross section at the center of the CFRP. At a few points are indicated a reversal of the coincidence of the strain, differing from the case of static behavior. When the strain distributions are drawn by joining the values at the center of each layer as shown by the broken line in Figure 23, the tendency of the distribution is similar to the distribution shown in Figure 20. Therefore, it is confirmed that the strain distribution obtained by the homogeneous model shows the non-homogeneous characteristics of the composite materials in an average sense.

Figures 24,25 and 26 show the states of the maximum shearing stress wave propagation. The velocity of the stress wave propagation in the material is varied by the construction of the reinforcement. And the difference of the velocity influences the interlaminar shearing stress.

Fig.21 - Strain(ϵ_x) history of the modeled CFRP.

Fig.22 - Strain(ϵ_x) history of the modeled GFRP.

Fig.23 - Instantaneous distribution of the strain(ϵ_x) in the section at the center for model 2.

Fig.24 - Propagation of maximum shearing stress (τ_{max}) for the model of resin.

Fig.25 - Propagation of maximum shearing stress (τ_{max}) for the model having continuous glass layers.

Fig.26 - Propagation of maximum shearing stress (τ_{max}) for the model having discontinuous glass layers.

Figure 27 shows the longitudinal strain response at 5mm away from the impact point in the composite materials constructed by two layers. At the early time when the compressive stress wave propagates only in the glass layer, the tensile stress occurs in the resin layer because the resin layer is pulled by the stress wave which passed through the glass layer previously. And as time passes, the difference between the strain occurring the glass and the one which occurred in the resin increases. And then it seems that the large shearing strain occurs at the interface between two layers. Moreover, that value is influenced by the construction of the reinforcement. Namely, as shown in Figure 28, the interlaminar shearing strain increases in the composite materials reinforced by continuous fiber.

Fig.27 - Instantaneous distribution on the impact direction strain on the section of 5 mm from the impact end for model showed above.

Fig.28 - Shearing strain history at the centroid of the interface resin element, 5 mm from the impact end, for models A and B.

From the above, we conclude the following. Namely in the GFRP reinforced by roving cloths, the interlaminar shearing strain increases because of having continuous fibers, and it makes for easy delamination, and the micro-buckling is promoted to occur easily.

In the hybrid composite materials, the stress wave propagation becomes more complex because of their complex laminations. Figure 29 shows the strain (ϵ_x) response on both surfaces of the composite materials. In this case, the large compressive strain occurs at the impact point comparing the tensile strain occurred on the back surface. Then it seems that the compressive strain makes a growth of cracks at the impact point easy in the hybrid composite materials. Figure 30 shows the shearing strain response occurring in the resin layer shown by a black point in the figure. The shearing strain increases at an early time, and the strain occurring in the material having continuous fibers is larger than that of model 5. But as observed experimentally, the first fracture occurs at the impact point of CFRP in the hybrid composite materials.

Fig.29 - Strain(ϵ_x) history of the models of hybrid composites.

Fig.30 - Shearing strain history of the resin element showed by black point, for model 3 and 5.

6. Conclusion

For the composite reinforced by various fibers under the impact bending load, various observation, experimentally and numerically, are obtained. The following is concluded:

(1) The stress wave propagation mechanism is influenced by the difference of the geometrical arrangement of the reinforcement, and it gives a factor deciding the strength and the fracture mode in GFRP. Especially, in GFRP reinforced by roving cloths, the fracture occurs near the impact point as a micro-buckling of the roving glass cloths.

(2) In CFRP, the first crack occurred at the impact point in the lateral direction to the fiber orientation.

(3) In the hybrid composite, not only the kind of GFRP which is used for the core material but also the laminated positions of CFRP influence the fracture mechanism, and the lamination of CFRP at the impact point is not effectively different from the case of statics.

(4) The analytical method adopted in this paper will be effective when the impact bending property of the composite having a non-homogeneous structure is taken into consideration.

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8. References

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SESSION 8:
ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS
AND STRUCTURES-II

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